

Behaviour of Halogeno-nitrobenzenes with *o*-Phenylenediamines: 5,10-Dihydrophenazines

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Several 5,10-dihydrophenazines have been synthesised by condensing halogeno-polynitrobenzenes with *o*-phenylenediamines. The intermediate diphenylamine derivatives have been separated and characterised. Structures of some of these compounds have also been established.

Claus¹ prepared 5,10-dihydrophenazines by reduction of phenazines. Subsequently these were prepared by condensation of *o*-phenylenediamines with catechol^{2,3}. Kehrman and Havas⁴ obtained them by condensing *o*-nitro- and *o*-amino-diphenylamines in presence of anhydrous sodium acetate. Several of such compounds were prepared with a view to testing their antifilaric activity⁵.

A simple method for their synthesis is by the condensation of *o*-phenylenediamine with reactive halogeno-benzene carrying a substituent (nitro or halogeno) in its *ortho* position. The first product of the reaction is a diphenylamine derivative, which cyclises to 5,10-dihydrophenazine⁴. The cyclisation takes place with the elimination of nitrous acid.

In course of studies on the behaviour of some halogeno-polynitrobenzenes with *o*-phenylenediamine and 4-methylphenylene-1,2-diamine, several new 5,10-dihydrophenazines have been synthesised (Tables I and II). The intermediate diphenylamine derivatives have also been isolated and characterised (Table III).

In the case of 4-methylphenylene-1,2-diamine, the amino group in *para* position to the methyl group takes part in the formation of diphenylamine derivatives⁶. Thus with picryl chloride, it provides 2,4,6-trinitro-4'-methyl-diphenylamine which then cyclises to 1,3-dinitro-7-methyl-5,10-dihydrophenazine.

1. *Ber.*, 1875, 8, 37.
2. Ris, *Ber.*, 1886, 19, 2206.
3. Hinsberg and Garfunkel, *Annalen*, 1896, 292, 258.
4. *Ber.*, 1923, 46, 341.
5. Morley, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1952, 4008.
6. Ernst, *Ber.*, 1890, 23, 3423.

TABLE I

5,10-Dihydrophenazines.

No.	Halogeno-nitrobenzene.	Product.	Yield.	M.P.	Colour.	Formula.	Found.	Reqd.
*1.	1-Chloro-2,4-dinitro-	2-Nitro-	80%	154°	Shining yellow	C ₁₂ H ₉ O ₂ N ₃	N : 18.24%	18.50%
2.	1-Chloro-2,6-dinitro-	1-Nitro-	70	158°	Chocolate	C ₁₂ H ₉ O ₂ N ₃	N : 16.37	16.50 ^b
3.	1,2-Dichloro-4,6-dinitro-	1,3-Dinitro-	85	205° (d)	"	C ₁₂ H ₇ O ₄ N ₄	N : 20.37	20.59
4.	1,3-Dichloro-4,6-dinitro-	2-Chloro-3-nitro-	90	228°	Orange-yellow	C ₁₂ H ₇ O ₂ N ₃ Cl	Cl : 13.20	13.58
5.	1,4-Dichloro-2,6-dinitro-	3-Chloro-1-nitro-	85	148°	Dark red	C ₁₂ H ₇ O ₂ N ₃ Cl	Cl : 13.32	13.58
*6.	1-Chloro-2,4,6-trinitro-	1,3-Dinitro-	90	205° (d)	Dark brown	C ₁₂ H ₇ O ₄ N ₄	N : 20.29	20.59
7.	1-Chloro-4,6-dinitro-2-methyl-	3-Nitro-1-methyl-	70	162-84°	Tan	C ₁₃ H ₁₁ O ₂ N ₃	N : 17.12	17.42
8.	1-Chloro-4,6-dinitro-3-methyl-	3-Nitro-2-methyl-	85	185°	Dark tan	C ₁₃ H ₁₁ O ₂ N ₃	N : 17.28	17.42
9.	1-Chloro-2,4,6-trinitro-5-methyl-	1,3-Dinitro-4-methyl-	90	205°	Dark brown	C ₁₃ H ₉ O ₄ N ₄	N : 19.30	19.58
10.	1,2-Dichloro-4,6-dinitro-5-methyl-	1,3-Dinitro-2-methyl-	75	142-44°	"	C ₁₃ H ₉ O ₄ N ₄	N : 19.40	19.58 ^b
11.	1,2,3-Trichloro-4,6-dinitro-	4-Chloro-1,3-dinitro-	85	208°	"	C ₁₃ H ₇ O ₄ N ₄ Cl	Cl : 11.32	11.58
12.	1,2,3-Tribromo-4,6-dinitro-	4-Bromo-1,3-dinitro-	80	196-97°	"	C ₁₃ H ₇ O ₄ N ₄ Br	Br : 22.54	22.79
13.	1,3-Dibromo-4,6-dinitro-5-methyl-	2-Bromo-3-nitro-4-methyl-	80	191°	Brown	C ₁₃ H ₉ O ₂ N ₃ Br	Br : 24.60	25.01
14.	1,3-Dichloro-2,4,6-trinitro-	2-Chloro-1,3-dinitro-	80	171-73°	Dark tan	C ₁₂ H ₇ O ₄ N ₄ Cl	Cl : 11.32	11.58

(d) denotes decomposition.

^bPrepared by the other method⁴.

^{*}Kebmann and Messinger (*Ber.*, 1893, 26, 2372) obtained it by reduction of 1,3-dinitrophenazine.

TABLE II

7-Methyl-5,10--dihydrophenazines.

No.	Halogeno-nitrobenzene.	Product.	Yield.	M.P.	Colour.	Formula.	Found.	Reqd.
1.	1-Chloro-2,6-dinitro-	1-Nitro-	75%	250° (d)	Fawn	$C_{13}H_{11}O_2N_5$	N : 17.40%	17.43%
2.	1-Chloro-2,4,6-trinitro-	1,3-Dinitro-	80	214°	Dark brown	$C_{13}H_{10}O_4N_4$	N : 19.34	19.58
3.	1,2-Dichloro-4,6-dinitro-	"	85	214°	"	"	N : 19.28	19.56
4.	1-Chloro-2-bromo-4,6-dinitro-	"	75	214°	"	"	N : 19.32	19.58
5.	1-Chloro-2-iodo-4,6-dinitro-	"	80	214°	"	"	N : 19.44	19.58
6.	1,3-Dichloro-4,6-dinitro-	2-Chloro-3-nitro-	85	185°	Golden yellow	$C_{13}H_{10}O_2N_3Cl$	Cl : 12.62	12.73
7.	1,4-Dichloro-2,6-dinitro-	3-Chloro-1-nitro-	70	185°	Brown	$C_{13}H_{10}O_2N_3Cl$	Cl : 12.55	12.73
8.	1-Chloro-4,6-dinitro-2-methyl-	3-Nitro-1-methyl-	65	230° (d)	Light brown	$C_{14}H_{13}O_2N_3$	N : 16.23	16.47
9.	1-Chloro-4,6-dinitro-3-methyl-	3-Nitro-2-methyl-	70	203°	Pale yellow	"	N : 16.20	16.47
10.	1-Chloro-2,6-dinitro-4-methyl-	1-Nitro-3-methyl-	60	210°	Brown	"	N : 16.34	16.47
11.	1-Chloro-2,4,6-trinitro-5-methyl-	1,3-Dinitro-4-methyl-	65	300° (d)	"	$C_{14}H_{13}O_2N_4$	N : 18.42	18.67
12.	1,2,3-Trichloro-4,6-dinitro-	4-Chloro-1,3-dinitro-	80	208°	Dark brown	$C_{13}H_9O_4N_4Cl$	Cl : 11.00	11.08
13.	2-Chloro-1,3-dibromo-4,6-dinitro-	4-Bromo-1,3-dinitro-	75	208°	Sepia	$C_{13}H_9O_4N_4Br$	Br : 21.05	21.92
14.	1,2-Dichloro-4,6-dinitro-5-methyl-	1,3-Dinitro-2-methyl-	55	190°	Dark tan	$C_{14}H_{12}O_4N_4$	N : 18.54	18.67
15.	2-Chloro-1-bromo-4,6-dinitro-5-methyl-	"	60	190°	"	"	N : 18.32	18.67
16.	1,4-Dichloro-2,6-dinitro-5-methyl-	3-Chloro-1-nitro-4-methyl-	60	300° (d)	Light brown	$C_{14}H_{12}O_2N_3Cl$	Cl : 12.09	12.26
17.	4-Chloro-1-bromo-2,6-dinitro-5-methyl-	"	60	300° (d)	"	"	Cl : 12.12	12.26
18.	1,4-Dibromo-2,6-dinitro-5-methyl-	3-Bromo-1-nitro-4-methyl-	75	250° (d)	Brown	$C_{14}H_{12}O_2N_3Br$	Br : 23.54	23.95
19.	1,3-Dibromo-4,6-dinitro-5-methyl-	2-Bromo-3-nitro-4-methyl-	80	> 300° (d)	Sepia	$C_{14}H_{12}O_2N_3Br$	Br : 23.49	23.95
20.	1,3-Dibromo-2,4,6-trinitro-5-methyl-	2-Bromo-1,3-dinitro-4-methyl-	85	"	Fawn	$C_{14}H_{11}O_4N_4Br$	Br : 21.00	21.11

TABLE III

Diphenylamines.

No.	Halogeno-nitrobenzene.	Diphenylamine.	X=2'-amino-4'-methyl- Colour.	M.P.	X=2'-amino- Colour.	M.P.
*1.	1-Chloro-2,4-dinitro-	X-2,4-dinitro-	Yellow	148°	..	..
2.	1-Chloro-2,4,6-trinitro-	X-2,4,6-trinitro-	Brown	116°	Light brown	153°
3.	1-Chloro-2,6-dinitro-	X-2,6-dinitro-	Fawn	125°	..	..
4.	1,2-Dichloro-4,6-dinitro-	X-2-chloro-4,6-dinitro-	Brown	132°	Light brown	118°
5.	1-Chloro-2-bromo-4,6-dinitro-	X-2-bromo-4,6-dinitro-	Sepia	180°	..	..
6.	1-Chloro-2-iodo-4,6-dinitro-	X-2-iodo-4,6-dinitro-	..	165°	Light sepia	152°
7.	1,3-Dichloro-4,6-dinitro-	X-3-chloro-4,6-dinitro-	Tan	181°	..	..
8.	1,4-Dichloro-2,6-dinitro-	X-4-chloro-2,6-dinitro-	Yellowish brown	165°	..	..
9.	1-Chloro-4,6-dinitro-2-methyl-	X-4,6-dinitro-2-methyl-	Dirty fawn	112°	Fawn	47°
10.	1-Chloro-4,6-dinitro-3-methyl-	X-4,6-dinitro-3-methyl-	Sepia	170°	Light brown	88°
11.	1-Chloro-2,6-dinitro-4-methyl-	X-2,6-dinitro-4-methyl-	Pale yellow	104°	Sepia	113°
12.	1-Chloro-2,4,6-trinitro-5-methyl-	X-2,4,6-trinitro-5-methyl-	Brown	120°	Light brown	150°
13.	1,2,3-Trichloro-4,6-dinitro-	X-2,3-dichloro-4,6-dinitro-	..	102°	Light yellow	96°
14.	2-Chloro-1,3-dibromo-4,6-dinitro-	X-2-chloro-3-bromo-4,6-dinitro-	Sepia	103°	..	..
15.	1,2-Dichloro-4,6-dinitro-5-methyl-	X-2-chloro-4,6-dinitro-5-methyl-	Yellow	102°	Pale yellow	95°
16.	1,4-Dichloro-2,6-dinitro-5-methyl-	X-4-chloro-2,6-dinitro-5-methyl-	Fawn	148°	Light sepia	121°
17.	4-Chloro-1-bromo-2,6-dinitro-5-methyl-	X-4-chloro-2,6-dinitro-5-methyl-	..	148°	..	121°
18.	1,4-Dibromo-2,6-dinitro-5-methyl-	X-4-bromo-2,6-dinitro-5-methyl-	Shining brown	142°	..	..
19.	1,3-Dibromo-4,6-dinitro-5-methyl-	X-3-bromo-4,6-dinitro-5-methyl-	Fawn	147°	..	..
20.	1,3-Dibromo-2,4,6-trinitro-5-methyl-	X-3-bromo-2,4,6-trinitro-5-methyl-	..	150°	..	..

 * Kourman and Messinger, *loc. cit.*

In the condensation of reactive halogeno-benzenes having a halogen atom and also a nitro group, *ortho* to the reactive halogen atom, the cyclisation always occurred by elimination of the halogen atom in preference to the nitro group⁷⁻⁹. Thus 1,2-dichloro- (or 1-chloro-2-bromo- or 1-chloro-2-iodo-), 1,2,3-trichloro-, 2-chloro-1,3-dibromo-, 1,2-dichloro- (or 2-chloro-1-bromo-) 4,6-dinitro-5-methylbenzenes with *o*-phenylenediamine furnish 1,3-dinitro-, 4-chloro-1,3-dinitro-, 4-bromo-1,3-dinitro-, and 1,3-dinitro-2-methyl-5,10-dihydrophenazines and with 4-methyl-1,2-phenylenediamine provide 1,3-dinitro-7-methyl-, 4-chloro-1,3-dinitro-7-methyl-, 4-bromo-1,3-dinitro-7-methyl-, and 1,3-dinitro-2,7-dimethyl-5,10-dihydrophenazine respectively.

In the case of halogeno-benzenes, which are unsymmetrically substituted and have two nitro groups in the *ortho* positions of the reactive halogen atom, formation of two isomeric dihydrophenazine derivatives is possible according as one or the other nitro group is involved in the cyclisation. Usually only one isomer, however, is the main product. Thus, 1-chloro-2,4,6-trinitro-5-methylbenzene, when condensed with *o*-phenylenediamine, can afford 1,3-dinitro-2-methyl- or 1,3-dinitro-4-methyl-5,10-dihydrophenazine. But the product obtained is different from 1,3-dinitro-2-methyl-5,10-dihydrophenazine, obtained by the condensation of 1,2-dichloro-4,6-dinitro-5-methylbenzene. Therefore it must be 1,3-dinitro-4-methyl-5,10-dihydrophenazine.

In the formation of similar heterocyclic compounds from reactive halogeno-toluenes, it has been observed¹⁰ that the nitro group in *ortho* position to the methyl is always the one which is involved in the cyclisation. Thus 1,3-dibromo-2,4,6-trinitro-5-methyl-, 1,4-dichloro-2,6-dinitro-5-methyl- and 1,4-dibromo-2,6-dinitro-5-methyl-benzenes with 4-methyl-1,2-phenylenediamine afford 2-bromo-1,3-dinitro-4,7-dimethyl-, 3-chloro-1-nitro-4,7-dimethyl-, and 3-bromo-1-nitro-4,7-dimethyl-5, 10-dihydrophenazine respectively.

*EXPERIMENTAL

A mixture of halogeno-nitrobenzene (0.01*M*), *o*-phenylenediamine (0.012*M*), and anhydrous sodium acetate (0.04*M*) in absolute ethanol (40 ml) was refluxed for 6 hr. The mass was cooled, filtered, and washed successively with water, HCl(dil.), and ethanol. The crude product was crystallised from a mixture of acetic acid and ethanol.

By carrying out the reaction for 20-30 min. only, the intermediate diphenylamine derivatives were obtained. These were generally crystallised from ethanol.

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*All melting points recorded are uncorrected.